

Women, Violence & Human rights

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Received : 09/04/2022

1st BPR : 25/04/2022

2nd BPR : 01/05/2022

Accepted : 16/05/2022

Abstract

India, with a population of 1.2 billion, is the world's second most populated country. The number, 120 million are women who live in poverty. Since an era, feminists have critiqued international human rights law for its "gender myopia." The core of these critiques has centered around conceptualization of human rights. At conceptual level, feminists challenge human rights law for fails recognize oppressive practices against women as human rights violations. Violence against women is an important public health problem with substantial consequences for women's physical, mental, sexual, and reproductive health that is increasingly being recognized as a serious human rights abuse. The problem is deeply embedded in cultures around the world, although its manifestation differs from one society to another. One of the most serious forms of violence targeted against women is acid violence.

Key words: Women, Violence & Human Rights

Introduction

India, with a population of 1.2 billion, is the world's second most populated country of the number, 120 million are women who live in poverty (Mulla,1987). India is one of the few countries where males significantly outnumber females, and this imbalance has increase other time. India's maternal mortality rates in rural areas are among the World's highest from a global perspective, Indian accounts for 19 percent of all lives births and 27 percent of all maternal death (Altekar, 1984). Since an era, feminists have critiqued international human rights law for its "gender myopia." The core of these critiques has centered around conceptualization of human rights. At conceptual level, feminists challenge human rights law for faili recognize oppressive practices against women as human rights violations (Hare et al., 1999). Violence against women is an important public health problem with substantial consequences for women's physical, mental, sexual, and reproductive health that is increasingly being recognized as a serious human rights abuse (Garcia et al.,2006 Salam et al., 2006). The problem is deeply embedded in cultures around the world, although its manifestation differs from one society to another. One of the most serious forms of violence targeted against women is acid violence. This type of violence has been endemic in South Asian countries (Bandyopadhyay et al., 2003).

Human Rights

Human Rights are "Rights and freedoms to which all humans are entitled." Proponents of the concept usually assert that everyone is endowed with certain entitlements merely by reason of being human (Ramachandran, 2002). Human rights are the core concept in international law, and have become even more prominent in the late twentieth century as a potential source of universal values for a globalised world (Steiner and Alston 2002; Donnelly 2003). Human Rights remain with both a statement of reality and an ever expanding set of objectives waiting to be actualized and their realization is possible only through a process of constant struggle. Human rights are violated not only by unjust acts but also by unjust national and international structures. Violations of human rights are not simple individual acts of violence. Such violations are generated by developmental models whether capitalist or socialist, which are weighted in favor of the state, orthose in power and are against poor, the marginalized, minorities, and women (Jha, 2002).

Human Rights and Women

A human being has a natural right to live from birth to death. In between is his life situation. Women rights are human rights. Promoting women rights calls for special attention. It has been an important area of focus for the whole world and international agencies (Jha, 2002). A number of reasons have been put forward to explain why the international human rights community has been slow to respond to women's global disadvantages. At the heart of the problem is the exclusion of women voices from the public world. Modern human rights law owes much to legacy of national pressure for civil and political rights at the end of eighteenth and early nineteenth century (Thomton et al, 1995). The exclusion of women from the public sphere cannot simply be noted as a matter of historical record because the impact of this historic exclusion of women continues to be felt in the underrepresentation of women in those public decision making bodies of the global community that frame the dimensions of human rights (Binion et al., 1995). The essence of the feminist critique of human rights law lies in the way in which it mediates the public and private spheres (Engle et al.,1993).

Women violence

The issue of domestic violence soon became a focus point for female scholars. Occurring both within the public and private spheres, vio against women is the most brutal manifestation of women's oppression violates a woman's right to bodily integrity and liberty; to torture, inhuman, and degrading treatment; and in its most acute form, it violates a woman's right to life. Yet violence against women was only formally recognized by the international community as a human rights issue (VDPA, 1993). The formal expression of this commitment can be found in the 1993 UN Declaration on the Elimination of Violence Against Women (Declaration on the Elimination of Violence Against Women, 1994) and Inter-American Convention on the Prevention, Punishment and Eradication of Violence Against Women (Inter-American Convention, 1994). Violence affects the lives of millions of women worldwide, in all socio-economic and educational classes, it cuts across cultural and religious barriers, impeding the right o women to participate fully in society. Violence against women takes a dismaying variety of forms, from domestic abuse and rape to child marriages and female circumcision. All are violations of the most fundamental human rights. Violence against women is a universal problem that must be universally condemned (Koomaraswamy et al., 2006). Women face the potential harms of torture and ill-treatment as evidenced by human rights instruments that offer redress for acts of violence committed against them by the state (Tomuschat et al., 2008).

Acid violence

Acid violence is a worldwide phenomenon that is not restricted to a particular race, religion, or geographic location. Although acid violence has been reported throughout South and Southeast Asia. Victims often do not report incidents to law enforcement authorities for fear of retaliation from the perpetrators. People in the community often do not help the victims for fear of harassment from the perpetrators, who may be more socially powerful than the victims. Despite the serious consequences of this problem, scientific literature on acid violence is scant.

Domestic violence

Violence against women in the family occurs in developed and developing countries alike. It has long been considered a private matter by by standers including neighbors the community and government. But such private matters have a tendency to become public tragedies. In the United States, a woman is beaten every is minutes. Indeed, domestic violence is the leading cause of injury among women of reproductive age in the United States. Between 22 and 35 per cent of women who visit emergency rooms are there for that reason.

According to the World Health Organization, 85 million to 115 million girls and women in the population have undergone some form of female genital mutilation and suffer from its adverse health effects. Every year an estimated two million young girls undergo this procedure. Most live in Africa

and Asia, but an increasing number can be found among immigrant and refugee families in Western Europe and North America. Indeed, the practice has been outlawed in some European countries (WHO, 2011).

Dowry related violence and early marriage

In some countries, weddings are preceded by the payment of an agreed-upon dowry by the bride's family. Failure to pay the dowry can lead to violence. In India, an average of five women a day is burned in dowry-related disputes—and many more cases are never reported. Early marriage, especially without the consent of the girl, is another form of human rights violation. Early marriage followed by multiple pregnancies can affect the health of women for life.

Violence in the community

Harassment in the workplace is a growing concern for women. Employers abuse their authority, sometimes promising promotions or other forms of career advancement or simply creating an uncomfortable and hostile work environment. In the United States, national statistics indicate that a woman is raped every six minutes. But in recent years more women have been coming forward to report such practices—some taking their case to court. In her report, the Special Rapporteur stressed that sexual harassment constitutes a form of discrimination (Gillum et al., 2008 Kliever et al., 2013).

Conclusion

Women upliftment is a big task ahead of us. It is multifarious dimensions. The issues relating to women need to be addressed with exceptional sensitivity taking into consideration all surrounding factors. Women from a major thick peace of society, their presume aspirations and problems cannot be ignored. It is imperative that they are looked upon as individuals engaged in gainful employment. They should be given due respect and status in society.

Conflict of Interest: The author has no conflict of interest.

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